

An efficient high-throughput grafting procedure for enhancing carbon fibre-to-matrix interactions in composites

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CARBON NEXUS

carbon fibre & composite research

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Background

- Carbon fibre as structural and superficial material
- Lightweight composites
- Always push to make stronger composites

Background

- Surface modification of carbon fibre to increase adhesion
 - Introduction of different functional groups to interact with resin
- Methods currently not amenable to large scale production
- Usually require expensive infrastructure, including safety concerns
- Our methods of electrochemistry are similar to inline processes
 - Diazonium electrografting

Surface modification

- Using diazonium salts
- Evaluate a method that may be easy to upscale
- Designed a compound easily detected by XPS
 - Fluorine not native to the surface

Synthesis

Synthesis

Surface modification

1 mg/mL
in MeCN
1 h, r.t.

- UV Treatment
- Heat Treatment
- Control
- Electrochemical Treatment

- XPS Analysis
- Young's Modulus
- Tensile Strength
- SEM imaging
- IFFS
- Molecular Modelling

-N₂ (g)

Carbon Fibre Surface

Carbon Fibre Surface

XPS analysis

Element	Control	UV	Heat	eChem
C	90.7%	89.4%	86.6%	87.9%
N	2.6%	2.9%	3.0%	2.7%
O	5.1%	6.0%	5.3%	7.1%
F	1.1%	1.3%	4.5%	1.2%
Si	0.4%	0.4%	0.4%	0.6%

Fibre Physical Properties

	Tensile Strength (Gpa)	Young's Modulus (Gpa)	Weibull Modulus (m)	Scale Parameter (σ)
Unsize Pristine	3.67 ± 0.11	262.6 ± 6.49	5.40	4.03
Control	3.90 ± 0.62	261.2 ± 7.09	8.30	3.13
UV Treated	2.50 ± 0.41*	258.4 ± 5.07*	8.19	2.71
Heat Treated	3.40 ± 0.61*	260.5 ± 11.68	7.64	3.67
eChem	3.76 ± 0.46	258.5 ± 7.31	5.32	3.82

SEM Imaging

Control

Heat Treated

UV Treated

Interfacial Shear Strength (IFFS)

Molecular Modelling

Carbon Fibre Surface

Pull-out displacement = 0 Å

Pull-out displacement = 40 Å

Summary

- Concise synthesis of diazonium salt
- Facile attachment of diazonium salt to surface
 - XPS
- Very low impact on fibre properties
 - Young's Modulus and Tensile strength
- Excellent increases in IFSS
- Published!

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Thank you for listening!
Questions?

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